

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

History of Political relations between Germany and Kazakhstan in 1991-2025

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Abstract. The following article demonstrated history of political relations of Germany and Kazakhstan in 1991-2025. There is a strong partnership between Kazakhstan and Germany based on trust, mutual support, and shared democratic values. political cooperation between the countries includes official visits and consultations, international forums, interparliamentary cooperation and security cooperation. Germany and Kazakhstan expressed satisfaction with cooperation within international organizations and agreed to continue to utilize opportunities for mutual support of initiatives and candidacies within the United Nations (UN), the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE), and other international organizations. In this scientific article, such methods as content analysis, historical-analytical method were used, which allowed to analyze the events, documents and sources of political relations between Kazakhstan and Germany.

Key words: Political, politics, democratic values, partnership, mutual support, trust, official visits, consultations, international forums

There is a strong partnership between Kazakhstan and Germany based on trust, mutual support, and shared democratic values.[1]

If to talk about some aspects of political cooperation between the countries:

- Official visits and consultations - Regular high-level official visits and consultations;
- International forums – two countries actively cooperate within international forums and organizations such as the UN, OSCE, and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization;
- Interparliamentary cooperation – There are parliamentary friendship groups in Kazakhstan Parliament (Kazakhstan-Germany) and the German Bundestag (Germany-Central Asia);
- Security cooperation – Kazakhstan and Germany maintain cooperation through the exchange of experience and practical measures between law enforcement agencies in the areas of security and the fight against terrorism and extremism.[2]

In 2024, 21 projects involving German capital were implemented in Kazakhstan, with a total investment of approximately 1 billion euro, covering sectors such as the production of building materials and valves.

If to talk about Joint Declaration on Cooperation between the Republic of Kazakhstan

and the Federal Republic of Germany, several aspects can be mentioned as:

- Political Dialogue
- Parliamentary Diplomacy
- Legal Cooperation
- Central Asia + Germany
- Security, Counterterrorism, and Drug Trafficking
- Economic Cooperation
- Energy
- Industry
- Climate, Environment, and Water Management
- Transport and Logistics
- Food and Agriculture
- Innovation, New Technologies, and Digitalization
- Finance
- Healthcare
- Science and Education
- Culture
- Visa
- Fundamentals of Technical Cooperation
- Final Provisions

Let's talk about political aspects deeper.

- Germany and Kazakhstan expressed satisfaction with cooperation within international organizations and agreed to continue to utilize opportunities for mutual support of initiatives and candidacies within the United Nations (UN), the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE), and other international organizations. They reaffirmed their commitment to the purposes and principles of the UN Charter, the Helsinki Final Act, and other documents adopted within the OSCE, as well as other universally recognized norms of international law.
- The Parties emphasize that universally recognized principles and norms of international law, democracy, human rights, and the rule of law as common values underlie bilateral relations. The Parties share the opinion that an active civil society, free media, and an independent judiciary make a significant contribution to the preservation of these values.[3]

If to demonstrate relations of Kazakhstan and Germany graphically it can be clearly seen that the connection between two parties has positive growth:

So, from the graph it can be clearly seen that relation of two sides has positive growth. If the correlation point was around 6 in 2022, in 2025 it reached 7.

If to talk about the **strengths and weaknesses** of each country, in terms of population it can be seen that the population of Germany is 4.46 bigger than the population of Kazakhstan (population of Germany: 83 783 942, population of Kazakhstan: 18 776 707). The land area of Kazakhstan is 7.74 bigger than the land area of Germany (land area

Graph1. Punctuation of historical relation between Kazakhstan and Germany[4]

(sq km) of Kazakhstan: 2 699 700, land area (sq km) of Germany: 348 672). Moreover, the position in the international influence ranking of Germany is 8, while Kazakhstan's is 70. So, 62 places lower. Additionally, Germany holds contact with 161 countries, while Kazakhstan has contact with 45 countries. Germany maintains positive relation with 46 countries, while Kazakhstan with 12.

If to talk about the history of relations between two sides, it can be seen that:

- On December 1, 1991, Germany recognized the state sovereignty of Kazakhstan.
- On February 11, 1992, diplomatic relations were established.
- In December 1992, the Embassy of Germany was opened in Almaty, which was moved to Astana in 2007.
- In September 1993, the Embassy Kazakhstan was opened in Bonn, and in 1999, it was relocated to Berlin.
- Since July 2022, N. Onzhanov has been the Ambassador of Kazakhstan to the Federal Republic of Germany.
- Since August 2021, M. Iversen has been the Ambassador of the Federal Republic of Germany to the Republic of Kazakhstan.[5]

If to talk about interparliamentary cooperation:

- **In 2015, 2017, 2018, 2019** Chairman of the Senate of the Parliament of the Republic of Kazakhstan K. Tokayev to participate in the Munich Security Conference in Germany.
- **In 2012** Chairman of the Mazhilis of the Parliament of the Republic of Kazakhstan N. Nigmatulin made an official visit to Germany.
- **In 2025** Deputy Chairman of the Mazhilis of the Parliament of the Republic of Kazakhstan – Special Representative of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan on the promotion of the candidacy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for non-permanent membership in the UN Security Council D. Nazarbayev made an official visit to Germany.
- **In 2010** President of the Bundestag N. Lammert made an official visit to Kazakhstan.

- **2015** Vice Presidents of the Bundestag J. Singhammer made an official visit to Kazakhstan.
- **In September, 2019** Vice Presidents of the Bundestag H.P. Friedrich made an official visit to Kazakhstan.
- **On February 19-21, 2023**, a delegation of the parliamentary group "Germany - Central Asia" visited the Republic of Kazakhstan.

There are parliamentary friendship groups in the Majilis of the Parliament of the Republic of Kazakhstan ("Kazakhstan-Germany") and the German Bundestag ("Germany-Central Asia").

And now let's talk about bilateral and multilateral cooperation of two sides.

- Kazakhstan and Germany actively cooperate within international organizations, including the UN, the UN Human Rights Council, the OSCE, and others.
- Kazakhstan co-sponsored the resolution on the Arms Trade Treaty, initiated by Germany.
- In December 2021, Germany abstained for the first time on the resolution "On the Universal Declaration on Achieving a Nuclear-Weapon-Free World," initiated by Kazakhstan.
- In 2007, Germany initiated the development of the EU Partnership Strategy for Central Asia and actively participated in the development of the new Strategy "The EU and Central Asia: New Opportunities for a Stronger Partnership."
- Kazakhstan is a member of the Bonn Initiative for a peaceful settlement in Afghanistan, launched by Germany in 2001.
- Germany initiated the Water Initiative for Central Asia (Berlin Process, 2008-2019).
- In January 2020, a presentation of the new German initiative, Green Central Asia, took place.[6]

Conclusion

There is a strong partnership between Kazakhstan and Germany based on trust, mutual support, and shared democratic values. political cooperation between the countries includes official visits and consultations - Regular high-level official visits and consultations; International forums – two countries actively cooperate within international forums and organizations such as the UN, OSCE, and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization; Interparliamentary cooperation – There are parliamentary friendship groups in Kazakhstan Parliament (Kazakhstan-Germany) and the German Bundestag (Germany-Central Asia); Security cooperation – Kazakhstan and Germany maintain cooperation through the exchange of experience and practical measures between law enforcement agencies in the areas of security and the fight against terrorism and extremism.

Germany and Kazakhstan expressed satisfaction with cooperation within international organizations and agreed to continue to utilize opportunities for mutual support of initiatives and candidacies within the United Nations (UN), the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE), and other international organizations.

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AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

Bosishga ruxsat etildi: 10.01.2026-yil.
Bichimi 70x100 1/16, "Times New Roman"
garniturada raqamli bosma usulida bosildi.
Shartli bosma tabog'i: 28,5. Adadi: 100.

"Noble Print" MChJ bosmaxonasida chop etildi.
100194, Toshkent shahri, Yunusobod-11, 62-uy.